

ELABORATION AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FLAX-PCL COMPOSITES AND SANDWICHES

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Elaboration

For composite or sandwich elaboration, flax fabrics (155*290mm²) and/or flax shives are stacked with Capa 6506 PCL powder inside a mold heated by induction (Roctool technology) and cooled down by a system of circulating water. This process allows a faster composite elaboration than classical heated presses. Exposure at 90°C is chosen at 5 min for flax fiber composites and at 10 min for shives composites and sandwich parts.

Two steps method for sandwich elaboration: 1) flax shives and PCL are pressed to manufacture the core, 2) flax fabrics and PCL are placed from either side of the core and pressed to form both faces and the sandwich simultaneously.

Tensile testing

3-points flexural testing

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{l^3}{48D} + \frac{l}{4N} \\ \frac{\delta'}{P'} = \frac{l'^3}{48D} + \frac{l'}{4N} \end{cases}$$

SAPCL2 sample is optimal for rigidity / weight according to Gibson-Ashby approach

			SAPCL2	SAPCL4
Sandwich thickness	d	mm	5.97	6.63
1 face thickness	t	mm	0.40	0.80
Core thickness	c	mm	5.17	5.03
Core density	ρ_c	g.cm ⁻³	0.824	0.846
Sandwich thickness	d	mm	5.97	6.63
Equivalent shear stiffness	N	Newtons	5722	6219
Equivalent flexural stiffness	D	N.mm ²	2.99E+06	1.24E+07
Shear strength	τ	MPa	0.839	1.038

Discussion and conclusions

Longitudinal tensile tests over PCL-flax UD composites give curves with a first curvature part followed by a quasi-linear part until rupture. These curves look very similar to the ones from tensile tests over flax fibers. Young's modulus values obtained with UD flax fibers and PCL are comparable to the ones with other matrices, in proportion with PCL rigidity.

During flexural testing, observed failure modes are either core failure or bond failure or mixed core-bond failure.

From equivalent shear stiffness, shear modulus of the core is deduced and equals to 40MPa. Compared to fiberboards (for example, wood particles-phenol formaldehyde composites), around 200MPa, G_c^* value for flax sandwiches should be optimized by other testing.

Equivalent flexural rigidity calculated from theoretical modelling and tensile testing values is lower than experimental values.

Further studies of PCL-flax sandwiches could be also undertaken for optimizing strength and impact properties and detect the differences and characteristics of PCL-flax sandwiches from classical combinations of foam-synthetic fibers composites.

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